

Consumer Awareness about Privacy and Security Risk for Online Shopping

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How to cite this paper: Mr. Robinson. M | Surya. R "Consumer Awareness about Privacy and Security Risk for Online Shopping" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.394-397, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd21695.pdf>

IJTSRD21695

ABSTRACT

This paper provides an analysis of shoppers perception on security and privacy problems in online shopping. The most objective of this analysis is to analyse the shoppers perceptions on security and privacy and formulate recommendations supported the findings that might contribute in eradicating these problems and boosting customer confidence. It additionally provides a quick discussion on the implications of online buying each customers and firms, the rising issues over privacy and security, and also the importance of shoppers perceptions on security and privacy problems in bolstering online searching adoption. Determining the perceptions of shoppers on security and privacy problems associated with e-commerce can profit IT security suppliers and internet businesses in crafting a multifarious approach in addressing those perceptions, one that effectively combines technological solutions and psychological approaches so as to resolve one among the last remaining obstacles to the widespread use of on-line shopping.

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Keywords: shoppers perception, technological solutions, online searching behaviour, perceived risk, trust & security, e-commerce, web site design.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online searching (sometimes called e-tail from "electronic retail" or e-shopping) may be a sort of electronic commerce that permits shoppers to directly obtain product or services from a vendor over the Internet using a web browser. Alternative names are: e-web-store, e-shop, e-store, net search, web-shop, web-store, on-line store, on-line shopfront and virtual store. Mobile commerce describes buying from an internet retailers mobile optimized online website or app.

An online store evokes the physical analogy of shopping for merchandise or services at a bricks-and-mortar merchant or store the method is named business-to-consumer online shopping. In the case wherever a business buys from another business the method is named business-to-business online searching. The largest of those on-line merchandising companies square measure Alibaba, Amazon.com and ebay.

PRIVACY AND SECURITY RISKS

Privacy risk is sometimes called intimacy risk. E-shops usually register all personal information of their customers, not only the data they are willing to give when finishing the acquisition forms, however conjointly information concerning their activity on the web site, making a profile for every client. This would not be such a big issue if the e-shops use the data only for their own interest, yet more frequently customer databases are sold to third parties, exposing consumers to unwanted advertising messages.

Security risk is additional or less connected to the monetary one. If financial risk discussed before referred to the probability of losing the money paid for a product because of product faults or low performance, security risk includes financial risk with a larger stake. When paying by master card over the net the consumer risks losing all the money in his bank account as his personal information can be stolen by hackers.

II. FACTORS AFFECTING ONLINE SHOPPING

The mysteries of the choices of the web shopper are speculative at the best as delving into the thought processes of every individual shopper is difficult to predict. on-line shopper behavior may be a difficult socio-technical development and has been the main target of researchers for the last decade. It is elusively exhausting making an attempt to judge the status of customers whereas they're creating purchases. Due to this tough task of creating generalized conclusions there has been variety of studies that have set out hypothesizing various factors. Previous analysis showed that buying behavior is additionally tormented by demographics, channel information, and looking orientation. However, there are several factors that are discernible which might lend to having higher dealing rates and having a glimpse into shopping behaviours.

FINANCIAL FACTOR

Financial factor is always the number one concern of individuals who are shopping online. Financial factor is defined as the perception that a certain amount of money could be lost while purchasing or making a product work properly from an online purchase. Certain age group are additional involved with their security and privacy of their bank account information. Millennials are additional doubtless to be less involved than older generations who behave additional skeptical in creating online purchases Shoppers are experiencing perceived risks for the potential loss they will expertise whereas shopping online.

PRODUCT FACTOR

The bonus of shopping in a ancient brick and mortar store is having the ability to own the product before the customer. This gives the chance to manage the expectations that a customer has once they are buying a product. When an ecommerce business gives accurate descriptions of products and the ability to zoom in on the product pictures to give the customers an accurate expectation of the product. Due to the restricted data that is typically conferred to consumers they lose the inability to judge the quality of the product.

CONVENIENCE

Convenience is the best aspect of online shopping. This is the main reason why people feel that online shopping is a major profit in their lives as a result of it saves them time throughout the day. Instead of having to travel out and take time beyond regulation buying a product people are able to save their time and pay it doing things they really wish to be doing. With such a high kind of differing kinds of stores there is close to each variety of product accessible online.

NON-DELIVERY

Although this isn't a common occurrence while shopping online not receiving their products after purchasing them online is a common fear shoppers share. Potential loss of a delivery is wherever products are lost or broken and make a concern in customers that they would not receive their products on the agreed time frame that the business stated. There are several factors that have an effect whether or not the customer receives their delivery for instance improper shipping and handling throughout transportation. With the variety of prospects that may fail the consumer might not complete a transaction based on delivery guarantees. Easing customers minds on shipping and non-delivery is by giving accurate updates on when they should expect the product they ordered.

RETURN POLICY

The return policy is the most significant issues that offers customers the flexibility to come an unwanted item or purchase that doesn't serve to their expectations or needs. Without a proper return policy, a customer's shopping behavior is severely stunted because they are forced to put too much faith into the ecommerce business, which is hard to achieve due to deception and falsely described products. There is nothing worse for the consumer than receiving a product and feeling like their money was wasted because the product doesn't measure up to expectations.

CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

Cultural differences and biases toward online shopping are prevalent with online stores being present in many countries around the world. Each societies value system is different,

but it is the ecommerce company's responsibility to provide an atmosphere that gives confidence to the customer. With 43% of buyers coming from non-English speaking countries there are many various cultural differences that require to be accounted for. Understanding the relationship that the consumer has with online shopping and the Internet in particular can affect consumer behaviour.

Individual shopping behaviours are hard to predict, but providing the needs of a customer and communicating properly all of the products details can minimize the behaviour of not purchasing goods. By eliminating the plain risks and considerations that the typical consumer has on a social-technical platform it reduces inessential hindrances that aren't personal.

III. PROBLEMS FACED IN ONLINE SHOPPING THE RISK OF HACK ATTACKS

Hackers will gain unauthorized access to your pc and trying to find ways that to interrupt into a network. They typically accomplish of these exploitation unpatched software system holes. Even non-technical individuals will accomplish a hack attack given the availability of information on-line on the techniques, malware and tools which will be used.

When conducting your online shopping, the private details you enter up for grabs. This can be a chance that hackers trying to find since they can hack the site you are using. They will then commit fraud by stealing sensitive personal information like your name, master card variety, address, contact details etc. They'll then use that information simulation to be you. Such an attack will cause a large money dent in your account.

PHISHING SCAMS

These are the most common reasonably cyber security threats that you just ought to use caution regarding once shopping on-line. The amount of phishing attacks is on the increase since they're simple to execute and may turn out the results that the attackers are trying to find while not abundant effort. It's terribly simple for a cybercriminal to form a page that resembles the real shopping website.

In a case like this, an unsuspecting customer can enter their personal details and bank details, and in this manner, they becomes a victim of a malware campaign or a web fraud. In alternative common situations, pretend emails containing an attachment or a link sent with the aim of tricking the receiving user into clicking them.

RANSOMWARE ATTACKS

Ransomware attacks became additional difficult and troublesome. This can be variety of attack that restricts access to your pc or your files. Hackers can then demand payment for the restriction to be removed. Cyber criminals can use web site popup advertisements and phishing emails that contain malicious attachments to trick internet buyers into gap them. Such pop ups and emails typically contain unbelievable deals that if clicked on can either lock the screen or encrypt files on the systems drive.

PRETEND ONLINE REVIEWS

Five-star ratings will do wonders for on-line retailers, therefore it pays to be sceptical of write-ups that lack detail, or too positive. If you're unsure regarding the validity of a review, attempt to check the supply, and trust your gut

feeling. If it doesn't appear right, the possibilities are the goods is substandard or it's going to even be a scam.

COUNTERFEIT MERCHANDISE

Huge steps are taken by on-line retailers to stay counterfeit product from their sites, however customers ought to still be aware of the chance of imitation merchandise. Where attainable, use prestigious retailers.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Maigan and Lukas (1997) studied on the buyer perception towards e-shopping. The study found that web searching involves a lot of uncertainty and risk than ancient searching. Consumers' temperament to provide their master card data over the online has been cited as a significant obstacle to online purchases.

Wolhandler (1999) web provides an enormous convenience for shopper because the main reason for the searching on-line has been united by most of investigator and customers. Because of the feature of web, it permits client to searching on-line anytime and anyplace, which suggests client will browse and searching on-line 24-hours on a daily basis, seven days per week from home or workplace, that attracts some time-starved shoppers come back to web for save time to looking merchandise in physical store.

Donthu and Garcia (1999) conducted the study on web Shoppers" and also the study found that the net shopper as older; create extra money, convenience seeker, innovative, impulsive, selection seeker, less complete and worth aware and with a lot of positive perspective towards advertising and marketing.

Bulkely and Carlton (2000) the bulk of web searching behaviours carries with it just one occasion purchases, that is especially per consumer's totally different searching motivations, like convenience. Therefore, the Ecommerce searching websites want improve their services or cut back the price of merchandise so as to motivating these sometime purchase shoppers to become loyal and regular customers.

Goldsmith (2000) within the study found that on-line innovators tend to exhibit the next level of authority. it's doubtless that these shoppers can believe that they possess the next level of information concerning searching and shopping for on-line and can purchase a lot of merchandise on the web. He found that innovative on-line patrons bought a lot of on-line.

Lee and Turban (2001) studied on trust in web searching and it had been found that lack of trust is one amongst the ordinarily cited reasons on why the customers don't like an on-line purchase and it plays a big role in facilitating online transactions. This may well be as a result of in an internet surroundings the customers haven't any physical interaction with the vendor. Therefore web site plays a vital role to achieve customers trust on-line.

Fareena (2002) investigated the determinants and role of shopper trust in e-business. The study has by trial and error incontestible that computing machine characteristics so considerably have an effect on perceptions of trust in an exceedingly computing machine. The study conjointly found that shopper characteristics like past expertise with the web and with a selected computing machine, do considerably have an effect on trust perceptions. the numerous finding of

the study that trusts is mediating variable between computing machine, shopper characteristics and shopper behaviour intent. The study conjointly contributes to understanding the scale of trust.

Man Kit Chang, Waiman Cheung & Vincent S. Lai (2005) within the paper Literature derived reference models for the adoption of on-line searching found that several vital variables had not been totally investigated. so as to support the event of on-line dealings and attract customers to shop for on-line, effort was place into the understanding of the dynamics of the adoption of on-line searching. A better understanding of the dynamics of the adoption call of on-line searching of the client can greatly profit its promotion and facilitate within the transition to a society more heavily concerned in electronic commerce.

Anthony D. Miyazaki & Ana Fernandez (2005)33, seen in his study that the govt. and business organizations have declared data privacy and security to be major obstacles inside the event of consumer-related e-commerce. Risk perceptions with reference to web privacy and security measure called issues for every new and difficult users of web technology. the present study reveals that vital relationship exists among consumers' levels of web experience, the use of alternate remote shopping for methods (such as phone and mail-order shopping), the perceived risks of on-line trying, and on-line shopping for activity.

Syed crowned head Alam & Zaharah Bakar (2008)51, have investigated in their study the relationships between young consumers' perceptions of the factors that influence their intention to buy for through on-line. The analytical results unit generally in step with consumers' perceptions of the shopper service, trustiness and trust of on-line shopping for. Trust has received the foremost consistent support as factors that influence on-line buying. Marketers have to be compelled to be compelled to know that net merchandising setting affects the means that customers scan and develop relationships.

Nik Kamariah Nik Mat (2005)28, studied that the higher computing device trust will turn out higher intention for on-line trying. The study provides the purchasers do not trust the online web site throughout on-line trying. is additionally another factors unit vital than trust like forms of merchandise. This result however is in contradiction with the result diagrammatical in various analysis that shows trust level might need a control on consumers' disposition to shop for and propensity to return to the situation.

V. CONCLUSION

Consumers tend to be fairly thoughtful decision makers, and therefore tend to avoid risk. In order for e-commerce to live up its full potential, online retailers need to understand that consumers perceive online purchasing as something of a threat, as was revealed in this study. In spite of the many retail opportunities the internet offers, growth of online purchasing will remain slow in emerging markets if marketers do not succeed to change the perception of risk associated with online purchasing. Online commerce in emerging markets will only thrive if marketers manage to expand consumer confidence and acceptance with regards to online purchasing.

In this study consumers online buying behaviour, with specific focus on the perceived risks consumers associate with online shopping were assessed. Specifically, the impact of perceived risk on online buying behaviour, and the impact of past online buying behaviour on future online buying behaviour were assessed. The results of the study revealed that personal, performance and social risk have an impact on online buying behaviour, and that past online buying behaviour impacted on future online buying behaviour. One can conclude that changing customers perceptions about perceived risks associated with online buying, and instilling confidence and acceptance about online commerce amongst consumers remain a challenge to marketers.

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